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ADHESION OF DISSIMILAR POLYMER-METAL COMPOSITE MATERIAL BY MECHANICAL INTERLOCKING

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Motivation

- This study is focused on developing and optimizing of polymer-metal composites (PMC) with strong interfacial adhesion by mechanism of mechanical interlocking.
- Engineering thermoplastic polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) and chemically etched aluminum alloy were used for the fabrication of the PMCs.

Objective

- Enhance adhesion between dissimilar organic and inorganic materials without the use of adhesives
- Optimization of fabrication processing conditions (temperature, pressure and time) for improved adhesion, evaluated by T-peel testing of the interfacial adhesion strength

Fabrication of PMCs

Lay-up of PMC samples for T-peel evaluation

Vacuum bagging compression molding

T-Peel Optimization Results

1. Temperature optimization

2. Pressure optimization

3. Time optimization

4. Compression/vacuum opt.

A. Smooth Aluminum

B. Etched Aluminum

C. PPS-Aluminum

Future Works

- Modeling of melt flow behavior of PPS with the micro-pore surface
- Investigate melt and solid state behavior of PPS on interfacial adhesion strength
- Addition of additives and reinforcement on adhesion behavior of other PMC

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